

1 RESEARCH ARTICLE

2

3 **Diverse soil seedbanks are resilient to reintroducing low-intensity fire in**
4 **a subtropical grassy woodland**

5

6 **Abstract**

7

- 8 1. In fire-prone ecosystems, reintroducing fire following long-term exclusion can restore
9 ecosystem function and biodiversity. In some situations, repeated burning might be
10 necessary to reduce invasive species and promote native plant re-establishment, but this
11 strategy rests on the assumption that residual seedbanks persist following fire.
- 12 2. We assessed the impact of a low-intensity prescribed fire on the below-ground germinable
13 seedbank, relative to the above-ground plant community in subtropical grassy woodlands of
14 southeast Queensland, Australia. Nine months after fire, we surveyed groundcover species
15 along ten transects (five burnt, five unburnt), each with three 1m² quadrats (30 total). Soil
16 samples were collected from three adjacent 1m² quadrats (30 total) and species in the soil
17 seedbank were identified during a five-month greenhouse emergence trial, concluding
18 when new germination slowed. We analysed species richness (α diversity), community
19 uniqueness (β diversity) and community composition in 13 trait groups (based on origin, life
20 span, growth form and N fixation) in response to 'fire' (burnt vs control) and 'position'
21 (above- vs below-ground).
- 22 3. There were no effects of fire on species richness of any group, either above- or below-
23 ground. There were significant effects of position on richness in all functional groups except
24 exotic grasses. Below-ground seedbanks had more than double the number of species,
25 compared to above-ground vegetation (e.g. an average of 27 vs 11 species per m² on
26 unburnt sites).
- 27 4. Above-ground vegetation had higher levels of uniqueness than below-ground seedbanks
28 and there were no notable effects of fire on β diversity in any functional group. Partitioning
29 β diversity showed that above-ground communities were structured by species
30 replacement, and below-ground seedbanks by richness agreement.
- 31 5. Seedbanks were compositionally dissimilar to above-ground plant communities (effect of
32 position on one Principal Component (PC1), $P < 0.001$) and composition was unaffected by
33 fire.
- 34 6. *Policy implications:* Seedbanks in this grassy woodland provide a rich biodiversity reservoir
35 which persisted after low-intensity fire. Patterns of species replacement suggest that
36 activities which diminish above-ground plant diversity (such as over grazing or conversion

37 to forest) will impact biodiversity at larger spatial scales, while soil seedbanks are likely
38 more robust to localised disruptions.

39
40 **Keywords:** beta diversity; community ecology; functional ecology; vegetation management; patch
41 mosaic burning; plant invasion; prescribed burning; restoration

42 43 **Introduction**

44
45 Fire has been present in Earth's terrestrial system for 420 million years (Bowman *et al.* 2009),
46 acting as an important evolutionary driver of the composition and functioning of ecosystems
47 (Bowman *et al.* 2016; Pausas and Keeley 2023). This is reflected in contemporary fire-prone
48 environments which often have distinctly high levels of biodiversity and endemism (He *et al.* 2019).
49 However, alteration of fire regimes due to climate change (Rovithakis *et al.* 2022; Pérez-Invernón
50 *et al.* 2023; Huang *et al.* 2025), land-use change (Braun *et al.* 2021), exotic species invasions
51 (Gaertner *et al.* 2014; Tomat-Kelly *et al.* 2021) and fire suppression (Diaz-Toribio *et al.* 2020) is
52 threatening thousands of plant and animal species with extinction (Kelly *et al.* 2020; Calhoun *et al.*
53 2022; Ensbey *et al.* 2023; Gibb *et al.* 2023). Appropriate fire management, including reintroducing
54 fire where it has been excluded, can sometimes restore ecosystem function by reducing invasive
55 plant biomass and promoting establishment of native species (Steffensen 2020; Stephens *et al.*
56 2021; Hodges *et al.* 2022; Dooley *et al.* 2023; Dairel and Fidelis 2024; Greenwood *et al.* 2024).
57 Prescribed burns, whereby fire is intentionally applied to vegetation, typically follow prescriptions
58 based on the frequency, intensity, and seasonality relevant to pre-disturbance or historical plant
59 communities, vegetation groups or key fire-response species (Conedera *et al.* 2009; Ryan *et al.*
60 2013; Elliott *et al.* 2020). However, most landscapes have changed so drastically through habitat
61 loss, fragmentation, and plant invasion that historical fire regimes may no longer be appropriate
62 (Keith and Henderson 2002; Freeman *et al.* 2017; Driscoll *et al.* 2021). New knowledge on how
63 contemporary ecosystems respond to fire is needed (Tubbesing *et al.* 2020), especially in the early
64 stages of reintroducing fire.

65
66 Invasive plant species are a key environmental factor complicating the reintroduction of fire. Some
67 woody invasive species are difficult to burn intentionally if they possess traits that reduce
68 flammability (Brooks *et al.* 2004; Mandle *et al.* 2011), such as *Triadica sebifera* (L.) in North
69 America (Fan *et al.* 2021) or *Lantana camara* (L.) in Australia (Berry *et al.* 2011). On the other
70 hand, plants that increase fuel biomass, connectivity and structure, such as invasive grasses, can
71 increase fire severity and frequency (Mahood *et al.* 2023). Increases in fire activity that accompany
72 plant invasion can inhibit the establishment of native species, facilitate further invasion, and
73 intensify changes in fire regimes in a process known as the 'invasive grass-fire cycle' (D'Antonio

74 and Vitousek 1992; Brooks *et al.* 2004; Mahood *et al.* 2023). In Northern Australia for example,
75 gamba grass (*Andropogon gayanus* (Kunth)) replaced short, sparse native grasses with a tall,
76 dense fuel bed, resulting in fuel loads three times higher than native plant communities (Setterfield
77 *et al.* 2010). Multiple invaders can also interact to change fire regimes. In native woodlands of
78 Hawaii USA, invasion of the bunchgrass *Schizachyrium condensatum* (Kunth) increased fire
79 frequency and subsequent recruitment of native species was inhibited by another invading
80 bunchgrass, *Melinis minutiflora* (P. Beauv) (D'Antonio *et al.* 2017). Therefore, reintroducing fire into
81 heavily invaded systems is often more complex than simply re-instating a historical fire regime,
82 because fires could either be hindered or promoted by invasive plant species.

83
84 In situations where invasive plant species complicate the reintroduction of fire, short-term burning
85 at frequencies higher than the historical rate (e.g. annual or biennial) has, in some cases, reduced
86 invasive plant biomass and promoted the re-establishment of native plant communities (Watson *et al.*
87 *et al.* 2009; Lewis *et al.* 2012a; Steffensen 2020; Ansley *et al.* 2021). This strategy aims to exploit
88 native species' traits (such as fire stimulated germination) that arose through a historical
89 association with fire, to promote regeneration of native communities and increase their resilience to
90 invasion (Prober and Lunt 2009; Brooks and Chambers 2011; Buisson *et al.* 2019; Lyons *et al.*
91 2023). Critically however, this approach rests on the assumption that native seedbanks are not
92 depleted after a single fire and remain sufficient to establish diverse and functional communities.
93 Soil seedbanks often act as 'biodiversity reservoirs', harbouring a diverse species pool even when
94 biodiversity declines in the above-ground plant community (Vandvik *et al.* 2016; An *et al.* 2022). In
95 theory, inter-fire intervals must be long enough for regenerating plants to reach maturity and
96 repopulate seedbanks (Ooi 2012). Burning before seedbanks are replenished risks local extinction,
97 especially for obligate-seeders which are killed by fire and regenerate only from seed (Lewis *et al.*
98 2012b; Ooi 2012). However, residual seedbanks (i.e. seeds remaining in the seedbank after a
99 majority have been depleted through post-fire germination) can persist if fire is applied at the right
100 time, frequency, and intensity (Auld and Denham 2006; Palmer *et al.* 2018; Plumanns Pouton *et al.*
101 2024). Knowledge about the potential for residual seedbanks to persist through a single fire is
102 therefore needed before frequent fire can be reintroduced into a system.

103
104 The extent to which soil seedbanks are impacted by fire depends on fire frequency (Santana *et al.*
105 2014; Kasel *et al.* 2024; Plumanns Pouton *et al.* 2024), fire severity (Shi *et al.* 2022;
106 Duivenvoorden *et al.* 2024), and properties of the seedbank like soil depth (Blodgett *et al.* 2000;
107 Auld and Denham 2006; Palmer *et al.* 2018). The influence of fire on soil seedbanks also varies
108 with plant traits such as mode of persistence (transient or persistent seed banks) (Lewis *et al.*
109 2012b), lifespan (Plumanns Pouton *et al.* 2024), seed coat characteristics (Ferrandis *et al.* 1999),
110 and the composition of above-ground vegetation (Ghasempour *et al.* 2022). Given the complexity

111 of seedbank responses to fire regimes, more research on seedbank dynamics is needed to
112 effectively guide fire management. This is especially the case in early stages of reintroducing fire,
113 where opportunities for knowledge sharing and learning can be translated into flexible fire
114 management decisions (Gillson *et al.* 2019; Oliveras Menor *et al.* 2025; Puig-Gironès *et al.* 2025).

115
116 In this study, we aimed to assess the impact of a prescribed burn on the below-ground germinable
117 seed bank, relative to the above-ground, plant community in a subtropical grassy woodland of
118 southeast Queensland, Australia. Compared with tropical savanna and temperate grassy
119 ecosystems, subtropical grassy woodlands have received little research attention and responses to
120 fire have been highly variable (Lewis and Debuse 2012; Lewis *et al.* 2012b; Fensham *et al.* 2017).
121 We aimed to determine whether a residual seed bank remained viable after a single fire. Following
122 the definition of resilience as ‘the rate at which a system returns to a reference state after
123 disturbance’ (Pimm 1984; Dakos and Kéfi 2022), we measured the richness, uniqueness and
124 composition of the germinable soil seedbank relative to unburnt control sites and to the above-
125 ground community. This encapsulated the ability of a seedbank to remain viable through fire,
126 measured by its ability to produce a similarly diverse community as unburned sites. Based on
127 literature regarding species traits and fire responses, we generated the following hypotheses to be
128 tested with field data:

- 129
130 1. Native species in the soil seedbank will be more resilient to fire than exotic species, reflecting
131 adaptations to fire in the Australian flora (e.g. fire stimulated germination (Gill 1975; Auld and
132 O'Connell 1991; Dixon *et al.* 1995; Morris 2000; Lamont *et al.* 2020; Ooi *et al.* 2022), and post-
133 fire reproduction (Clarke *et al.* 2015);
- 134 2. Annual species in the soil seedbank will be more resilient to fire than perennial species,
135 reflecting their rapid growth and reproduction (Milberg and Hansson 1994; Morgan 1998;
136 Catford *et al.* 2019) and propensity for long-lived seed (Dwyer and Erickson 2016;
137 Plumanns Pouton *et al.* 2024);
- 138 3. Given that legumes typically have long-lived seed and heat-responsive physical dormancy (Bell
139 1999; Santana *et al.* 2010; Ooi *et al.* 2014; Pausas and Lamont 2022), leguminous species
140 should show a greater difference in seedbank diversity between burnt and unburnt sites than
141 non-leguminous species;
- 142 4. Soil seedbanks will have lower species richness (α diversity) than the above ground plant
143 community, reflecting the difficulty of sampling the soil comprehensively (Vandvik *et al.* 2016),
144 but the degree of uniqueness (β diversity) in seedbanks will be higher, reflecting long-term
145 accumulation of seed storage during fire exclusion (Dölle and Schmidt 2009; Heydari *et al.*
146 2017; Lee *et al.* 2024).

147

148 In examining community uniqueness, we also partitioned β diversity into richness difference and
149 replacement components (Podani and Schmera 2011; Legendre and De Cáceres 2013), to provide
150 process-informed restoration guidance (da Silva *et al.* 2018). Ultimately, results from this study will
151 provide information to land managers on the risks to the soil seedbank when reintroducing fire;
152 critical information required when using fire management to improve plant biodiversity.

153

154 **Methods**

155

156 *Study system*

157

158 This study took place at a 3,091 ha Nature Refuge within Hidden Vale Research Station, in
159 Southeast Queensland, Australia (Maccoll and Tribe 2017) (Fig. 1). The climate is subtropical, with
160 mean minimum and maximum temperatures of 6.3 – 20.8 °C in the coldest month (July) and 26.2 –
161 31.7 °C in the hottest month (January) (Bureau of Meteorology 2024). The area receives a mean
162 annual rainfall of 759 mm, peaking in the summer months, with February being, on average, the
163 wettest month (Bureau of Meteorology 2024).

164

165 The property is a grazing station and is currently managed for pastoral production and land
166 restoration. Our study took place in ungrazed grassy woodlands on young basaltic soils, where
167 narrow-leaved ironbark (*Eucalyptus crebra*) and silver-leaved ironbark (*E. melanophloia*) form
168 mixed stands with yellow box (*E. melliodora*) and Moreton Bay ash (*Corymbia tessellaris*)
169 (Queensland Regional Ecosystems 12.8.16 and 12.8.17, Neldner *et al.* 2019). Common native
170 grasses include black speargrass (*Heteropogon contortus*), kangaroo grass (*Themeda triandra*),
171 Queensland wiregrass (*Aristida queenslandica*), scented top (*Capillipedium spicigerum*) and forest
172 bluegrass (*Bothriochloa bladhii*). Other common species include sedges (*Scleria mackaviensis*,
173 *Cyperus gracilis*), herbaceous legumes (*Galactia tenuiflora*, *Glycine tabacina*, *Desmodium varians*,
174 *Rhynchosia minima*) and herbs (*Hydrocotyle laxiflora*, *Lobelia spp.*). Dominant invasive plant
175 species include red natal grass (*Melinis repens*), the woody shrub lantana (*Lantana camara*), and
176 the herbs *Bidens pilosa* and *Gomphocarpus fruticosus*.

177

178 *Study design*

179

180 In 2022, a prescribed burning program began at the property, aiming to reduce fire fuel loads and
181 promote native biodiversity within grassy woodlands. There were no records of fire at the property
182 for at least 10 years before the program began. Areas identified for burning were located around
183 gullies and valleys to minimise wildfire risk in Semi-evergreen Vine Thicket (Queensland Regional
184 Ecosystem 12.8.21, Neldner *et al.* 2019), a fire-sensitive dry rainforest listed as Endangered in

185 Queensland (*Vegetation Management Act* 1999). The burning program began with a 40 ha pilot
186 burn in August of 2022 (Fig. 1) and the current study focussed on this area, aiming to inform
187 ongoing fire management at the property though long-term monitoring. We established ten 100m
188 sampling transects, each with three sampling points, across approximately 70 ha (Fig. 1). Sites
189 were paired, each with one control (no fire) and one burn treatment. The fire was conducted during
190 winter to maintain low-intensity fire that would not impact trees, while having sufficient grass curing
191 to carry fire. As this was a pilot burn, we were unable to collect pre-fire data because the long-term
192 monitoring study had not yet started when the burn took place. Nonetheless, we wanted to
193 leverage this trial burn to provide information on seedbank responses in the early stages of the
194 program. Thus, our study represents a space-for-time approach, comparing burned areas to
195 nearby unburned areas, rather than before-after-control-impact, given the early stage at which we
196 worked on the experiment. Hereafter, 'above-ground' refers to the standing vegetation
197 (groundcover, tree and shrub species) and 'below-ground' refers to the soil seedbank.

198
199 At each of the 10 transects, we selected three above-ground sampling points at 20m, 60m and
200 100m along the central axis of the transect (Fig. 1). Each sampling point comprised a 1m² quadrat
201 for measuring groundcover species (predominantly grasses and forbs), nested within a 5m²
202 quadrat for measuring tree and shrub species. Three 1m² below-ground soil sampling quadrats
203 were established adjacent to each above-ground point, parallel along the transect. A 1m buffer
204 between the above- and below-ground quadrats was established, to minimise impact on the
205 above-ground quadrats. At one control transect the three quadrats were spaced 40m, 80m and
206 100m due to a logistical error, but the associated above-ground data (collected during a larger
207 monitoring study) were used to account for this. This design resulted in 30 sampling quadrats each
208 for the above and below ground surveys.

209
210 Vegetation surveys were undertaken by an experienced botanist over six days across two weeks in
211 May of 2023. The identity of all groundcover species and visual estimates of their percentage cover
212 were recorded in each 1m² quadrat. All groundcover taxa were identified to species level, where
213 possible (Rose *et al.* 2011; Rose and Rose 2020; Leiper *et al.* 2022). The number and identity of
214 tree and shrub species was recorded within 5m² quadrats to provide insight into taxa which were
215 distributed, and affected by disturbance, at a larger scale. While the above- and below-ground
216 plant communities were sampled across a standardised 1m² area, the above ground community in
217 our analysis included the additional shrub and tree species at the 5m² scale. We considered the
218 implications of these additional species when interpreting results.

219

220 *Soil sampling*

221

222 Soil samples were collected on 14 June 2023, 18 days after the above-ground surveys concluded,
223 and nine months post-fire. Some seed rain is likely to have occurred in the 9-month period
224 between the fire and soil sampling, contributing new seeds to the soil seedbank. Since this would
225 also be occurring on unburnt control sites, our approach represents a comparison of burnt and
226 unburnt soil seedbanks that include both residual (pre-fire) seed and new seed from recent seed
227 rain. The soil sampling protocol was designed to account for the heterogeneous nature of
228 seedbanks that arise from complex and irregular above-ground vegetation in grasslands (Plue and
229 Hermy 2012; Vandvik *et al.* 2016). In each of the 30 x 1m² soil sampling quadrats, we sampled 30
230 soil cores in a 5 x 6 grid pattern (approximately 17-20 cm apart), using a 55mm diameter foot
231 auger. This high number of small soil cores per m² aimed to increase sampling precision by
232 accounting for patchy seed distribution (Bigwood and Inouye 1988). The grid pattern achieved a
233 sampling effort (area of soil sampled relative to area of above-ground vegetation sampled) of
234 approximately 5%, which is considered adequate for biodiversity assessments (Vellend *et al.* 2008;
235 Plue and Hermy 2012). While sampling efforts of ~5% are common in seedbank studies (Vandvik
236 *et al.* 2016), such low sampling rates can reduce the accuracy of comparisons to above-ground
237 vegetation. For this study however, using the same sampling effort across treatments ensured we
238 could meaningfully compare burnt and unburnt areas to inform management. Soil cores were taken
239 to a depth of 5cm, appropriate for grassland sampling (Pywell *et al.* 1997) and used widely in other
240 grassland studies (e.g. Thompson 1986; Wills and Read 2007; Plue and Hermy 2012; Plue *et al.*
241 2017). The 30 cores extracted from each quadrat were pooled and mixed thoroughly, resulting in
242 30 pooled samples (one per quadrat).

243

244 *Emergence trial*

245

246 We conducted an emergence trial to measure the readily germinable seedbank. This approach
247 favours generalist species over those with specialised germination requirements (Plue *et al.* 2017),
248 but was considered sufficient to provide a comparative analysis of burnt and unburnt sites. Species
249 richness estimates from emergence trials typically increase with trial length (Plue *et al.* 2017) and
250 trial lengths vary substantially, from 3 months to 3-years (Mahé *et al.* 2021). Our emergence trial
251 lasted for five months, from the end of August 2023 to the end of January 2024, when new
252 germination had slowed substantially (Carrasco-Puga *et al.* 2021). Morphospecies identification
253 continued until 4th April 2024 (details below).

254

255 After field collection, soil samples were air dried for one month in open plastic bags in a
256 glasshouse, and soil was turned weekly to ensure even and consistent drying (De Vitis *et al.* 2020).

257 Once condensation ceased, samples were kept in a cool, dark storage room for one month. Holed
258 trays (35cm x 29.5cm and 5cm high) were prepared with two layers of shade cloth to prevent
259 sediment loss (Orr *et al.* 1996). Trays were filled with 4cm (~2.5L) of washed sand that
260 approximated the sandy topsoil of the region's vertosols (Dalling *et al.* 1995; Orr *et al.* 2004; Page
261 *et al.* 2006). Each pooled soil sample was halved by weight, and each half spread over one of two
262 trays to depth of 1cm (Dalling *et al.* 1995). Filled trays were labelled and placed randomly on a
263 glasshouse bench. Two control trays containing only sand and shade cloth were placed alongside
264 sample trays to monitor contamination (none of which was detected). We did not apply dormancy
265 breaking treatments (Orr *et al.* 2010; Moreira and Pausas 2012), but since the burn treatment
266 samples had been exposed to fire *in situ*, some level of dormancy breaking might have occurred
267 naturally.

268
269 The emergence trial began in the last week of August 2023 (end of Austral winter) and ran through
270 summer, to accommodate species with cool and warm germination requirements. Temperatures in
271 the glasshouse ranged from 8.2–48.7°C, with mean day (6am–6pm) and night (6pm–6am)
272 temperatures of 28.9°C and 15.6°C, respectively. The watering regime was designed to keep soil
273 moist, to prevent seedling mortality and to enable rapid germination (and thus did not necessarily
274 match field conditions). To initiate the trial, misters were run for several minutes until trays were
275 saturated. During the trial, misters ran at least twice a day for 3–4 minutes. We increased watering
276 up to 4 times a day in summer after a small mortality event indicated conditions were too dry.

277
278 Seedlings were removed when they were large enough to be identified or differentiated to
279 morphospecies, but not so large as to interfere with emergence of other seedlings (Davies *et al.*
280 2013; Carrasco-Puga *et al.* 2021). In most cases, seedlings were too small for identification upon
281 removal, so we developed a classification system based on morpho-species to count and identify
282 species. Each week, adequately sized seedlings were assigned a morpho-species, photographed,
283 transplanted to a labelled pot, and allowed to grow until identification was possible. The morpho-
284 species label was then used for all individuals of that species, each of which was counted upon
285 removal and recorded. Three people were involved in species identification: two experienced plant
286 scientists (including the same botanist who conducted the above-ground plant surveys) and the
287 lead author of the study. We used published literature (Stanley and Ross 1983; Hacker 1990;
288 Leiper *et al.* 2022) and online resources (Simon and Alfonso 2011; Brisbane City Council 2024;
289 PlantNet 2024) to identify species.

290

291 *Functional group classification*

292

293 Each species was classified into groups, based on traits which influence the response to fire in
294 above- and below-ground plant communities (Table 1). Trait groups were based on: origin
295 (native/exotic), life span (annual/perennial), growth form (grass, forb) and ability to fix N
296 (legume/non-legume) (Simon and Alfonso 2011; Brisbane City Council 2024; PlantNet 2024). Taxa
297 were assigned to 13 functional groups based on these categories in a hierarchical way. For
298 example, we analysed the diversity of all taxa, native taxa and exotic taxa separately, while
299 grasses were further divided into native and exotic categories (Table 1). This allowed us to
300 examine broad responses while also examining which functional traits drove broader patterns. We
301 did not analyse shrubs and trees and shrubs as a separate growth form category because our
302 sampling method focussed on ground cover species. Nor did we analyse sedges and rushes
303 separately because there were only 8 species overall. However, these groups were included in
304 calculations for the higher level classifications, such as total species richness.

305

306 *Analysis*

307

308 To investigate the resilience of the soil seedbank to fire, we analysed species richness (α
309 diversity), community uniqueness (β diversity) and community composition (from Principal
310 Components) of soil seedbanks relative to the above ground plant community. All data were
311 analysed at the quadrat level (30 observations per position, 60 observations total). We used linear
312 (LMM) and generalised linear mixed models (GLMM) in R (R Development Core Team 2024), with
313 a different model family and link function for each response variable (details below). The same
314 model structure and approach was followed for all response variables. We began by fitting a global
315 model using three fixed effects: fire (a two level factor: control, burn), position (a two-level factor:
316 above, below), and an interaction between these terms (fire x position). When the interaction was
317 insignificant ($P > 0.05$), we removed that term and fitted a final model in an additive form (fire +
318 position). We did not simplify the model further as fire and position were the two primary design
319 variables. We considered final model terms to be significant when $P < 0.05$. All models included a
320 random effect for transect to account for spatial non-independence. We used predictSE in the
321 `AICmcmoavg` package (Mazerolle 2023) to visualise the estimated mean and standard error
322 from each final model.

323

324 For each functional group, we modelled species richness (α diversity) using a GLMM with a
325 poisson distribution and logit link function, suitable for count data bounded by zero with an
326 unbounded upper limit (McCullagh 2019), in `lme4` (Bates *et al.* 2015).

327

328 Because the above and below ground data were measured differently (proportion cover and
329 abundance, respectively), we analysed β diversity and community composition as binary data
330 indicating presence (1) or absence (0) of each species. For each functional group, we calculated
331 the Local Contribution to β diversity (LCBD) representing the degree of uniqueness for each
332 quadrat (Legendre and De Cáceres 2013). LCBD ranges from zero to one, with higher values
333 indicating greater uniqueness. We derived LCBD values in *adespatial* (Dray *et al.* 2025) from a
334 Jaccard dissimilarity matrix, suitable for binary data (Anderson *et al.* 2011). By conducting this
335 analysis on the entire 60 quadrat sample, the regional species pool (γ) was defined as total
336 species richness, including both levels of the fire treatment (control, burn) and position (above,
337 below). This definition of γ is suitable for identifying biotic and abiotic filters that shape patterns of
338 community assembly (such as species losses and gains under different management regimes) at
339 spatial scales where dispersal is possible (Cornell and Harrison 2014). This allowed γ to reflect that
340 seed from the above ground community becomes available to the seedbank below ground, while
341 species in the seedbank are available to recruit above ground. LCBD was analysed for each
342 functional group using GLMM with a beta distribution and logit link function (for continuous,
343 numeric data, bounded by 0 and 1) (Cribari-Neto and Zeileis 2010) in *glmmTMB* (Brooks *et al.*
344 2017; McGillicuddy *et al.* 2025). We also partitioned the Jaccard dissimilarity matrix into
345 replacement and richness difference components using the Podani family indices (Podani and
346 Schmera 2011; Legendre 2014) in *adespatial* (Dray *et al.* 2025), to provide insight into the
347 process underlying changes in community uniqueness.

348

349 To evaluate community composition, Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was conducted using
350 'prcomp' in base R. Prior to fitting the PCA, we fitted the quadrat by species matrix (60 x 117) to a
351 Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) in *vegan* (Oksanen *et al.* 2024) to determine the level
352 of homogeneity in the data (Lepš and Šmilauer 2003). The length of the first DCA axis was 2.86
353 suggesting homogeneity and appropriateness of PCA for our data set (Lepš and Šmilauer 2003).
354 The first three principal components (PC) were plotted to visualise community dissimilarity between
355 control and burnt sites and between the above- and below-ground communities. The first three
356 PCs were then modelled, with the PC scores used as response variables in three separate LMMs
357 to test the effect of fire and position on the community composition. The PC scores were modelled
358 with a Gaussian error distribution (for continuous, unbounded numeric data) in *lme4* (Bates *et al.*
359 2015).

360

361 **Results**

362

363 A total of 117 plant species was identified during this study, of which 35 were common to both the
364 above- and below-ground plant communities (Table 1, Fig. 2). In the emergence trial, 73 species

365 were identified, with an additional 121 morphospecies remaining unidentified. Many of the
366 unidentified morphospecies were likely duplicates, so the total number of unidentified species is
367 likely much lower. Throughout the emergence trial, 20,369 individuals germinated, of which
368 identified species comprised 80.9% (16,373). In the above-ground dataset, 78 species were
369 identified (Fig. 2), with two unidentified morphospecies. Among identified species in the overall
370 data set, forbs ($n=64$) and grasses ($n=29$) were numerically dominant, and 63% of species were
371 native ($n=74$) (Table 1).

372
373 The interaction term (fire x position) was not significant in any of the models of species richness (α
374 diversity), thus the final model was the additive model (fire + position) for all functional groups
375 (Table 2, Fig. 3a, Fig. S1). No significant effects of burn treatment on species richness were
376 identified for any functional group (Table 2). There was a significant effect of position on species
377 richness in functional groups ($P < 0.001$), except for exotic grasses ($P = 0.706$) (Table 2). The effect
378 was positive in all cases (Fig. S1), with below-ground seedbanks having higher species richness
379 than their above-ground counterparts, regardless of burn status (Fig. 3a).

380
381 There was a significant interaction between fire and position on LCBD (β diversity) for exotic
382 grasses ($P = 0.044$, Table 3), showing greatest β diversity above-ground on burnt sites, but no
383 position effect on control sites (Fig. S2i). For all functional groups except exotic grasses, the
384 interaction term (fire x position) was insignificant for LCBD ($P > 0.05$, Table 3), and the final model
385 was the additive form (fire + position) (Fig. 3b, Fig. S2). These additive models all included a
386 significant effect of position on LCBD ($P < 0.05$), showing lower β diversity in the seedbank than
387 the associated above-ground community (Fig. 3b, Fig. S2). For all functional groups with additive
388 models, there was no effect of fire on β diversity ($P > 0.05$, Table 3, Fig. 3b, Fig. S2). Above-
389 ground plant communities were structured strongly by species replacement with low levels of
390 similarity (Fig. 4a). Below-ground plant communities were structured strongly by richness
391 agreement, and were intermediate along the nestedness-replacement axis (Fig. 4b). When
392 comparing above- and below-ground communities, richness differences were most notable and
393 these communities had little similarity (Fig. 4c).

394
395 The PCA showed that the first three Principal Components explained 39.06% of variation in overall
396 community dissimilarity. There was obvious clustering by position along PC1, demonstrating
397 marked dissimilarity between above- and below-ground communities, while burnt and unburnt
398 samples were similar within positions (Fig. 5). Linear mixed models indicated no significant
399 interactive effects of fire and position on any of the three PCs ($P > 0.05$). There was a significant
400 main effect of position on PC1 ($P < 0.001$), demonstrating that this axis explained dissimilarity

401 between above- and below-ground communities. The main effect of fire was not significant on PC1
402 ($P = 0.86$). There were no fire or position effects on PC2 or PC3.

403

404 **Discussion**

405

406 One year after a low intensity prescribed fire, soil seedbanks in a subtropical grassy woodland,
407 Australia, had comparable species richness and community composition to unburnt areas. These
408 effects were consistent among functional groups, thus, hypotheses that (H1) native and (H2)
409 annual species would be more resilient to fire than exotic and perennial species, respectively, were
410 not supported. The hypothesis that (H3) fire would have a stronger effect on leguminous than non-
411 leguminous species was also not supported, with both groups being unaffected by fire. Seedbanks
412 harboured notably high biodiversity at a small scale (1 m²), with more than double the number of
413 species, compared to above-ground vegetation (e.g. an average of 27 vs 11 species per m² on
414 control sites). This was despite the above-ground plant community including additional tree and
415 shrub species recorded at a 5 m² scale, and despite the full suite of species below-ground not
416 being included due to time constraints on germination and identification. Thus, our hypothesis (H4)
417 that α diversity would be lower in the seedbank because of sampling limitations was not supported.
418 We also anticipated that long-term accumulation of soil-stored seed would create compositionally
419 unique seedbanks but this was also not supported. Compositional uniqueness was generally low in
420 soil seedbanks relative to above-ground vegetation, regardless of burn status. Together, these
421 results suggest that soil seedbanks in these grassy woodlands are resilient to the reintroduction of
422 low-intensity fire.

423

424 Despite being species poor relative to the seedbank, above-ground vegetation in this study
425 harboured high levels of uniqueness, reflected in high Local Contribution to β diversity. Uniqueness
426 in the above-ground vegetation was driven mainly by species replacement (i.e. few shared species
427 among quadrats) rather than differences in richness. A similar result was found for ground layer
428 vegetation in subtropical grasslands of South Africa, which had a limited response to burning but a
429 high degree of species replacement (Ward *et al.* 2023). From a restoration perspective, this
430 indicates high conservation value at large scales across the grassy woodlands we studied here
431 (Baselga 2010; Legendre 2014). Activities which diminish above-ground plant diversity at one site
432 (such as over grazing or conversion to forest) (McIntyre *et al.* 2003; Zhou *et al.* 2022; Prangel *et al.*
433 2023), will have a larger impact on total biodiversity in this system, than if the community was
434 structured by differences in species richness (da Silva *et al.* 2018). Localised disruptions are less
435 likely to negatively impact the soil seedbank because they are species rich and relatively similar
436 from site to site.

437

438 Contrary to our results, some studies have found that fire reduces above-ground β diversity,
439 resulting in compositional similarity (Wester *et al.* 2014). In North American mixed conifer forests
440 for example, reductions in β diversity post-fire were attributed to increasing fire severity (Weeks *et al.*
441 *et al.* 2023). For soil seedbanks, both increases and decreases in β diversity following fire have been
442 reported (Myers *et al.* 2015; Lee *et al.* 2024), the latter due to the replacement of rarer species with
443 common or 'disturbance-tolerant' species. In tropical dry forests of northeast Brazil, for example, β
444 diversity decreased in seedbanks after fire, possibly because fire-tolerant species, such as those
445 with small seed size and seed hardness, survived fire and became dominant (Bezerra *et al.* 2022).
446 In our study, patterns in both α and β diversity were overwhelmingly driven by their position above
447 or below ground, not by fire. The only exception to this pattern was for exotic grasses, where
448 increases in above ground β diversity were only evident on burnt sites (Fig. S2i). However, we
449 never recorded more than two exotic grass species on a given quadrat, so statistical power was
450 low to detect patterns in this group. Seedbanks were dominated by several weedy species with
451 very high seed production, dispersal rates, and persistence (*Melinis repens* (Stokes *et al.* 2011),
452 *Cyperus gracilis* (Alessio Leck and Schütz 2005), *Conyza bonariensis* (Wu *et al.* 2007), *Bidens*
453 *Pilosa* (Gurvich *et al.* 2004)). This, along with dispersal from outside the sampled areas, might
454 have contributed to low levels of uniqueness in the soil seedbank (Lee *et al.* 2024).

455
456 Annual species are often common in soil seedbanks due to their reliance on seed stores for
457 regeneration (Milberg and Hansson 1994; Morgan 1998; Humphrey and Schupp 2001; Sternberg
458 *et al.* 2003; Tessema *et al.* 2012; Rawson *et al.* 2013; Plumanns Pouton *et al.* 2024) but we found
459 a diverse perennial soil seedbank with comparatively fewer annual species (Fig. S1). Only 4 of the
460 19 annual species identified in this study were native, which is not particularly surprising in this
461 perennial dominant system. Annual species in the soil seedbank have been found to decline with
462 time since disturbance (Cowan *et al.* 2023) and native annuals in our study might have been
463 depleted during the long time since the last major disturbance (at least 10 years, possibly much
464 more). Perennial grasses dominated the above-ground vegetation in our study sites (*Themeda*
465 *triandra*, *Heteropogon contortus*, *Bothriochloa bladhii*, *Aristida queenslandica* and *Capillipedium*
466 *spicigerum*), and these do not typically have long-lived soil seedbanks (McIvor and Gardener 1994;
467 Morgan and Williams 2015). These species represented only 1.6% of total seedbank abundance,
468 or, in the case of *Themeda triandra*, none at all. *Themeda* seed can have morpho-physiological
469 dormancy (Cole and Lunt 2005) making them typically rare in readily germinable soil seedbank
470 (Morgan 1998). Since we did not apply targeted dormancy breaking during the emergence trial, it
471 could have been present in the soil but failed to germinate. Australian perennial grasses typically
472 resprout rapidly after fire or germinate from short-lived seed, rather than relying on long-lived soil
473 seedbanks (Morgan and Williams 2015). The perennial species in the seedbank in this study
474 largely represented perennial forbs, which form more persistent seedbanks than grasses (Peco *et*

475 *al.* 1998). The five most abundant forb species in this study accounted for 37% of the identified
476 seedbank abundance. There was generally no effect of fire related to lifespan, either in the above-
477 or below-ground plant communities.

478

479 Species richness of leguminous and non-leguminous forbs was equally resilient to fire. Among
480 hard seeded legumes, the proportion of species with heat released physical dormancy is lower in
481 tropical and subtropical grasslands (42%) than in crown fire ecosystems (86%) (Pausas and
482 Lamont 2022). These observations suggest that physical dormancy might be less important for
483 germination in this subtropical grassland system. Alternatively, the fire at our study site might not
484 have been hot enough at depth to break dormancy (80-100°C, Ooi *et al.* 2014), resulting in strong
485 residual seedbanks of leguminous and non-leguminous species.

486

487 Some seedbank studies have reported low species richness relative to above-ground vegetation
488 because of difficulties in adequately sampling the soil seedbank (Wills and Read 2007). Sampling
489 effort and species richness are usually correlated in seedbank studies (Butler and Chazdon 1998;
490 Page *et al.* 2006; Vandvik *et al.* 2016), but ecological patterns can be detected even with only 50%
491 of species surveyed (Vellend *et al.* 2008). Studies across semi-natural grasslands, heathlands and
492 forests of temperate Europe, for example, found similarly high seedbank diversity as we found
493 here, even with lower sampling effort (e.g. 2.8% Plue and Hermy 2012). With a sampling effort of
494 approximately 5%, our results suggest that moderate sampling effort might be adequate to
495 characterise seedbank species richness in Australian subtropical grassy woodland ecosystems.

496

497 A number of limitations need to be considered in interpreting the high soil seedbank diversity
498 reported in this study. Seedlings growing in glasshouse conditions (high moisture, temperature and
499 fertiliser) might have been larger or morphologically different than those in the field, potentially
500 causing identification errors. However, cross-verification among three identifiers likely minimised
501 this problem. Seedling identification and morphospecies classification was challenging, and might
502 have led to inaccuracies in below-ground data. However, we were cautious in assigning
503 morphospecies and continuing to grow individuals until identification was possible and only used
504 species presences, not abundance, in the analysis. In fact, given that we excluded unidentified
505 morphospecies that were confirmed to be different species from the analysis, actual seedbank
506 richness was probably even higher than reported here. The finding that fire did not negatively
507 influence seedbanks or above-ground vegetation is unlikely to have been a result of any human
508 error because our methods were consistent across treatments. Such results are not uncommon in
509 the literature for seedbanks (e.g. Lewis *et al.* 2012b), or above-ground communities (Penman *et al.*
510 2008; Watson and Wardell-Johnson 2008; Cury *et al.* 2020) and indicate that low-intensity annual
511 fire allowed for adequate recovery in both seedbanks and above-ground vegetation.

512

513 Soil seedbanks are critical for post-fire recovery in plant communities and effective fire
 514 management should not deplete native soil seedbanks. Our study found that seedbanks in a
 515 grassy woodland in southeast Queensland, Australia, were highly species rich and provide a
 516 reservoir of biodiversity for post-fire regeneration. Seedbanks subjected to a low-intensity
 517 prescribed fire remained species rich, suggesting that a second fire in the near term is unlikely to
 518 negatively impact seedbank biodiversity. Subtropical grasslands can take decades to respond to
 519 disturbance (Ward *et al.* 2023), so monitoring the impact of management in this system is critical.
 520 Patterns of species replacement in the above ground plant community suggest that activities which
 521 diminish above-ground plant diversity will impact biodiversity at larger spatial scales, while soil
 522 seedbanks are likely more robust to localised disruptions.

523

524 **References**

525

526 Allesio Leck M, Schütz W (2005). Regeneration of *Cyperaceae*, with particular reference to seed
 527 ecology and seed banks. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 7, 95-133.

528 An H, Baskin CC, Ma M (2022). Nonlinear response of the soil seed bank and its role in plant
 529 community regeneration with increased grazing disturbance. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 59, 2593-
 530 2603.

531 Anderson MJ, Crist TO, Chase JM, Vellend M, Inouye BD, Freestone AL, Sanders NJ, Cornell HV,
 532 Comita LS, Davies KF, Harrison SP, Kraft NJB, Stegen JC, Swenson NG (2011). Navigating the
 533 multiple meanings of β diversity: a roadmap for the practicing ecologist. *Ecology Letters* 14, 19-28.

534 Ansley RJ, Boutton TW, Hollister EB (2021). Can prescribed fires restore C4 grasslands invaded
 535 by a C3 woody species and a co-dominant C3 grass species? *Ecosphere* 12, e03885.

536 Auld TD, Denham AJ (2006). How much seed remains in the soil after a fire? *Plant Ecology* 187,
 537 15-24.

538 Auld TD, O'Connell MA (1991). Predicting patterns of post-fire germination in 35 eastern Australian
 539 *Fabaceae*. *Australian Journal of Ecology* 16, 53-70.

540 Baselga A (2010). Partitioning the turnover and nestedness components of beta diversity. *Global*
 541 *Ecology and Biogeography* 19, 134-143.

542 Bates D, Mächler M, Bolker B, Walker S (2015). Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4.
 543 *Journal of Statistical Software* 67, 1-48.

- 544 Bell DT (1999). The process of germination in Australian species. *Australian Journal of Botany* 47,
545 475-517.
- 546 Berry ZC, Wevill K, Curran TJ (2011). The invasive weed *Lantana camara* increases fire risk in dry
547 rainforest by altering fuel beds. *Weed Research* 51, 525-533.
- 548 Bezerra JS, Arroyo-Rodríguez V, Tavares JM, Leal A, Leal IR, Tabarelli M (2022). Drastic
549 impoverishment of the soil seed bank in a tropical dry forest exposed to slash-and-burn agriculture.
550 *Forest Ecology and Management* 513, 120185.
- 551 Bigwood DW, Inouye DW (1988). Spatial pattern analysis of seed banks: an improved method and
552 optimized sampling. *Ecology* 69, 497-507.
- 553 Blodgett H, Hart-Fredeluces G, Stanislaw M (2000). Annual burning decreases seed density in the
554 upper soil layers of the seed bank. *Tillers, Grinnel College* 2, 31-38.
- 555 Bowman DMJS, Balch JK, Artaxo P, Bond WJ, Carlson JM, Cochrane MA, D'Antonio CM, DeFries
556 RS, Doyle JC, Harrison SP, Johnston FH, Keeley JE, Krawchuk MA, Kull CA, Marston JB, Moritz
557 MA, Prentice IC, Roos CI, Scott AC, Swetnam TW, van der Werf GR, Pyne SJ (2009). Fire in the
558 Earth system. *Science* 324, 481-484.
- 559 Bowman DMJS, Perry GLW, Higgins SI, Johnson CN, Fuhlendorf SD, Murphy BP (2016).
560 Pyrodiversity is the coupling of biodiversity and fire regimes in food webs. *Philosophical*
561 *Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 371, 20150169.
- 562 Braun AC, Faßnacht F, Valencia D, Sepulveda M (2021). Consequences of land-use change and
563 the wildfire disaster of 2017 for the central Chilean biodiversity hotspot. *Regional Environmental*
564 *Change* 21, 37.
- 565 Brisbane City Council, 2024. Weed Identification Tool Brisbane City Council, Brisbane.
566 <https://weeds.brisbane.qld.gov.au/>, accessed February 2024.
- 567 Brooks ME, Kristensen K, Van Benthem KJ, Magnusson A, Berg CW, Nielsen A, Skaug HJ,
568 Mächler M, Bolker BM (2017). glmmTMB balances speed and flexibility among packages for zero-
569 inflated generalized linear mixed modeling. *The R Journal* 9, 378-400.
- 570 Brooks ML, Chambers JC (2011). Resistance to invasion and resilience to fire in desert shrublands
571 of North America. *Rangeland Ecology & Management* 64, 431-438.
- 572 Brooks ML, D'Antonio CM, Richardson DM, Grace JB, Keeley JE, DiTomaso JM, Hobbs RJ,
573 Pellant M, Pyke D (2004). Effects of invasive alien plants on fire regimes. *Bioscience* 54, 677-688.

- 574 Buisson E, Le Stradic S, Silveira FAO, Durigan G, Overbeck GE, Fidelis A, Fernandes GW, Bond
575 WJ, Hermann J-M, Mahy G, Alvarado ST, Zaloumis NP, Veldman JW (2019). Resilience and
576 restoration of tropical and subtropical grasslands, savannas, and grassy woodlands. *Biological*
577 *Reviews* 94, 590-609.
- 578 Bureau of Meteorology, 2024. Climate Data Online. Australian Government.
579 <http://www.bom.gov.au/climate/>, accessed February 2024.
- 580 Butler BJ, Chazdon RL (1998). Species richness, spatial variation, and abundance of the soil seed
581 bank of a secondary tropical rain forest. *Biotropica* 30, 214-222.
- 582 Calhoun KL, Chapman M, Tubbesing C, McInturff A, Gaynor KM, Van Scoyoc A, Wilkinson CE,
583 Parker-Shames P, Kurz D, Brashares J (2022). Spatial overlap of wildfire and biodiversity in
584 California highlights gap in non-conifer fire research and management. *Diversity and Distributions*
585 28, 529-541.
- 586 Carrasco-Puga G, Díaz FP, Soto DC, Hernández-Castro C, Contreras-López O, Maldonado A,
587 Latorre C, Gutiérrez RA (2021). Revealing hidden plant diversity in arid environments. *Ecography*
588 44, 98-111.
- 589 Catford JA, Smith AL, Wragg P, Clark AT, Kosmala M, Cavender-Bares J, Reich PB, Tilman D
590 (2019). Traits linked with species invasiveness and community invasibility vary with time, stage and
591 indicator of invasion in a long-term grassland experiment. *Ecology Letters* 22, 593-604.
- 592 Clarke PJ, Lawes MJ, Murphy BP, Russell-Smith J, Nano CEM, Bradstock R, Enright NJ, Fontaine
593 JB, Gosper CR, Radford I, Midgley JJ, Gunton RM (2015). A synthesis of postfire recovery traits of
594 woody plants in Australian ecosystems. *Science of The Total Environment* 534, 31-42.
- 595 Cole BI, Lunt ID (2005). Restoring Kangaroo Grass (*Themeda triandra*) to grassland and woodland
596 understoreys: a review of establishment requirements and restoration exercises in south-east
597 Australia. *Ecological Management & Restoration* 6, 28-33.
- 598 Conedera M, Tinner W, Neff C, Meurer M, Dickens AF, Krebs P (2009). Reconstructing past fire
599 regimes: methods, applications, and relevance to fire management and conservation. *Quaternary*
600 *Science Reviews* 28, 555-576.
- 601 Cornell HV, Harrison SP (2014). What are species pools and when are they important? *Annual*
602 *Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 45, 45-67.

- 603 Cowan EL, Miller BP, Fontaine JB, Enright NJ, Standish RJ (2023). Soil seed bank development of
604 smoke-responsive plant species in a 23-year restoration chronosequence and implications for
605 resilience to fire. *Applied Vegetation Science* 26, e12713.
- 606 Cribari-Neto F, Zeileis A (2010). Beta regression in R. *Journal of Statistical Software* 34, 24.
- 607 Cury RTDS, Montibeller-Santos C, Balch JK, Brando PM, Torezan JMD (2020). Effects of fire
608 frequency on seed sources and regeneration in southeastern Amazonia. *Frontiers in Forests and*
609 *Global Change* 3.
- 610 D'Antonio CM, Ostertag R, Cordell S, Yelenik S (2017). Interactions Among Invasive Plants:
611 Lessons from Hawai'i. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 48, 521-541.
- 612 D'Antonio CM, Vitousek PM (1992). Biological invasions by exotic grasses, the grass/fire cycle,
613 and global change. *Annual Review of Ecology Evolution and Systematics* 23, 63-87.
- 614 da Silva PG, Hernández MIM, Heino J (2018). Disentangling the correlates of species and site
615 contributions to beta diversity in dung beetle assemblages. *Diversity and Distributions* 24, 1674-
616 1686.
- 617 Dairel M, Fidelis A (2024). Fire stimulates seedling recruitment from the seed bank in the Cerrado.
618 *Journal of Vegetation Science* 35, e13268.
- 619 Dakos V, Kéfi S (2022). Ecological resilience: what to measure and how. *Environmental Research*
620 *Letters* 17, 043003.
- 621 Dalling JW, Swaine MD, Garwood NC (1995). Effect of soil depth on seedling emergence in
622 tropical soil seed-bank investigations. *Functional Ecology* 9, 119-121.
- 623 Davies RJP, Whalen MA, Mackay DA, Taylor D, Pisanu P (2013). Does soil seed bank diversity
624 limit post-fire regeneration in small, fragmented, long-unburnt remnants of fire adapted vegetation?
625 *Biological Conservation* 158, 287-295.
- 626 De Vitis M, Hay FR, Dickie JB, Trivedi C, Choi J, Fiegenger R (2020). Seed storage: maintaining
627 seed viability and vigor for restoration use. *Restoration Ecology* 28, S249-S255.
- 628 Diaz-Toribio MH, Carr S, Putz FE (2020). Pine savanna plant community disassembly after fire
629 suppression. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 31, 245-254.
- 630 Dixon KW, Roche S, Pate JS (1995). The promotive effect of smoke derived from burnt native
631 vegetation on seed germination of Western Australian plants. *Oecologia* 101, 185-192.

- 632 Dölle M, Schmidt W (2009). The relationship between soil seed bank, above-ground vegetation
633 and disturbance intensity on old-field successional permanent plots. *Applied Vegetation Science*
634 12, 415-428.
- 635 Dooley M, Lewis T, Schmidt S (2023). Fire frequency has a contrasting effect on vegetation and
636 topsoil in subcoastal heathland, woodland and forest ecosystems, south-east Queensland,
637 Australia. *Austral Ecology* 48, 1865-1887.
- 638 Dray S, Bauman D, Blanchet G, Borcard D, Clappe S, Guénard G, Jombart T, Larocque G,
639 Legendre P, Madi N, Wagner HH, 2025. adespatial: Multivariate Multiscale Spatial Analysis. R
640 package version 0.3-28. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=adespatial>.
- 641 Driscoll DA, Armenteras D, Bennett AF, Brotons L, Clarke MF, Doherty TS, Haslem A, Kelly LT,
642 Sato CF, Sitters H, Aquilué N, Bell K, Chadid M, Duane A, Meza-Elizalde MC, Giljohann KM,
643 González TM, Jambhekar R, Lazzari J, Morán-Ordóñez A, Wevill T (2021). How fire interacts with
644 habitat loss and fragmentation. *Biological Reviews* 96, 976-998.
- 645 Duivenvoorden E, Wagner B, Nitschke CR, Kasel S (2024). Short-interval, high-severity wildfires
646 cause declines in soil seed bank diversity in montane forests of south-eastern Australia. *Forest*
647 *Ecology and Management* 553, 121627.
- 648 Dwyer JM, Erickson TE (2016). Warmer seed environments increase germination fractions in
649 Australian winter annual plant species. *Ecosphere* 7, e01497.
- 650 Elliott M, Lewis T, Venn T, Srivastava SK (2020). Planned and unplanned fire regimes on public
651 land in south-east Queensland. *International Journal of Wildland Fire* 29, 326-338.
- 652 Ensbey M, Legge S, Jolly CJ, Garnett ST, Gallagher RV, Lintermans M, Nimmo DG, Rumpff L,
653 Scheele BC, Whiterod NS, Woinarski JCZ, Ahyong ST, Blackmore CJ, Bower DS, Burbidge AH,
654 Burns PA, Butler G, Catullo R, Chapple DG, Dickman CR, Doyle KE, Ferris J, Fisher DO, Geyle
655 HM, Gillespie GR, Greenlees MJ, Hohnen R, Hoskin CJ, Kennard M, King AJ, Kuchinke D, Law B,
656 Lawler I, Lawler S, Loyn R, Lunney D, Lyon J, MacHunter J, Mahony M, Mahony S, McCormack R,
657 Melville J, Menkhorst P, Michael D, Mitchell N, Mulder E, Newell D, Pearce L, Raadik TA, Rowley
658 JLL, Sitters H, Southwell DG, Spencer R, West M, Zukowski S (2023). Animal population decline
659 and recovery after severe fire: Relating ecological and life history traits with expert estimates of
660 population impacts from the Australian 2019-20 megafires. *Biological Conservation* 283, 110021.
- 661 Fan Z, Yang S, Cheng N, Liu X, Song A, Dong L (2021). Invasibility of fire-managed ecosystems to
662 the Chinese tallow tree (*Triadica sebifera*) in the lower Gulf Coastal Plain, USA: Mechanisms and
663 key factors at the landscape level. *Forest Ecology and Management* 479, 118539.

- 664 Fensham RJ, Butler DW, Laffineur B, MacDermott HJ, Morgan JW, Silcock JL (2017). Subtropical
665 native grasslands may not require fire, mowing or grazing to maintain native-plant diversity.
666 *Australian Journal of Botany* 65, 95-102.
- 667 Ferrandis P, Herranz J, Martínez-Sánchez J (1999). Effect of fire on hard-coated Cistaceae seed
668 banks and its influence on techniques for quantifying seed banks. *Plant Ecology* 144, 103-114.
- 669 Freeman J, Kobziar L, Rose EW, Cropper W (2017). A critique of the historical-fire-regime concept
670 in conservation. *Conservation Biology* 31, 976-985.
- 671 Gaertner M, Biggs R, Te Beest M, Hui C, Molofsky J, Richardson DM (2014). Invasive plants as
672 drivers of regime shifts: identifying high-priority invaders that alter feedback relationships. *Diversity
673 and Distributions* 20, 733-744.
- 674 Ghasempour M, Erfanzadeh R, Török P (2022). Fire effects on soil seed banks under different
675 woody plant species in Mazandaran province, Iran. *Ecological Engineering* 183.
- 676 Gibb H, Grubb JJ, Black D, Porch N, Decker O, McGeoch M, Deane D, Murphy N (2023).
677 Rainforest litter invertebrates decimated by high severity burns during Australia's gigafires. *Austral
678 Ecology* 48, 1328-1343.
- 679 Gill AM (1975). Fire and the Australian flora: a review. *Australian Forestry* 38, 4-25.
- 680 Gillson L, Whitlock C, Humphrey G (2019). Resilience and fire management in the Anthropocene.
681 *Ecology and Society* 24.
- 682 Greenwood L, Bliege Bird R, McGuire C, Jadaï N, Price J, Skroblin A, van Leeuwen S, Nimmo D
683 (2024). Indigenous pyrodiversity promotes plant diversity. *Biological Conservation* 291, 110479.
- 684 Gurvich DE, Enrico L, Funes G, Zak MR (2004). Seed mass, seed production, germination and
685 seedling traits in two phenological types of *Bidens pilosa* (Asteraceae). *Australian Journal of
686 Botany* 52, 647-652.
- 687 Hacker JB, 1990. A Guide to Herbaceous and Shrub Legumes of Queensland. University of
688 Queensland, St Lucia, Queensland.
- 689 He T, Lamont BB, Pausas JG (2019). Fire as a key driver of Earth's biodiversity. *Biological Reviews*
690 94, 1983-2010.
- 691 Heydari M, Omidipour R, Abedi M, Baskin C (2017). Effects of fire disturbance on alpha and beta
692 diversity and on beta diversity components of soil seed banks and aboveground vegetation. *Plant
693 Ecology and Evolution* 150, 247-256.

- 694 Hodges JA, Price JN, Nicotra AB, Guja LK (2022). Smoke and heat can increase germination of
695 common wildflowers and grasses—implications for conservation and restoration of critically
696 endangered grassy ecosystems. *Ecological Management & Restoration* 23, 94-99.
- 697 Huang K, Xiaoyang W, Liqiang Z, Hao G, and Qu Y (2025). Increasing risk of global forest loss
698 from extreme wildfires under climate change. *International Journal of Digital Earth* 18, 2483982.
- 699 Humphrey LD, Schupp EW (2001). Seed banks of *Bromus tectorum*-dominated communities in the
700 Great Basin. *Western North American Naturalist* 61, 85-92.
- 701 Kasel S, Fairman TA, Nitschke CR (2024). Short-interval, high-severity wildfire depletes diversity of
702 both extant vegetation and soil seed banks in fire-tolerant eucalypt forests. *Fire* 7, 148.
- 703 Keith DA, Henderson MK (2002). Restoring the prepastoral condition: response to Jurskis. *Austral*
704 *Ecology* 27, 691-693.
- 705 Kelly LT, Giljohann KM, Duane A, Aquilué N, Archibald S, Batllori E, Bennett AF, Buckland ST,
706 Canelles Q, Clarke MF, Fortin M-J, Hermoso V, Herrando S, Keane RE, Lake FK, McCarthy MA,
707 Morán-Ordóñez A, Parr CL, Pausas JG, Penman TD, Regos A, Rumpff L, Santos JL, Smith AL,
708 Syphard AD, Tingley MW, Brotons L (2020). Fire and biodiversity in the Anthropocene. *Science*
709 370, eabb0355.
- 710 Lamont BB, Pausas JG, He T, Witkowski ETF, Hanley ME (2020). Fire as a selective agent for both
711 serotiny and nonserotiny over space and time. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences* 39, 140-172.
- 712 Lee S, Klinger R, Brooks ML, Ferrenberg S (2024). Homogenization of soil seed bank communities
713 by fire and invasive species in the Mojave Desert. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 12.
- 714 Legendre P (2014). Interpreting the replacement and richness difference components of beta
715 diversity. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 23, 1324-1334.
- 716 Legendre P, De Cáceres M (2013). Beta diversity as the variance of community data: dissimilarity
717 coefficients and partitioning. *Ecology Letters* 16, 951-963.
- 718 Leiper G, Glazebrook J, Cox D, 2022. Mangroves to mountains: a field guide to the native plants of
719 south-east Queensland. Native Plants Queensland Logan River Branch.
- 720 Lepš J, Šmilauer P, 2003. Multivariate Analysis of Ecological Data using CANOCO. Cambridge
721 University Press, Cambridge.
- 722 Lewis T, Debuse VJ (2012). Resilience of a eucalypt forest woody understorey to long-term (34–55
723 years) repeated burning in subtropical Australia. *International Journal of Wildland Fire* 21, 980-991.

- 724 Lewis T, Reif M, Prendergast E, Tran C (2012a). The effect of long-term repeated burning and fire
725 exclusion on above- and below-ground Blackbutt (*Eucalyptus pilularis*) forest vegetation
726 assemblages. *Austral Ecology* 37, 767-778.
- 727 Lewis TOM, Reif M, Prendergast E, Tran C (2012b). The effect of long-term repeated burning and
728 fire exclusion on above- and below-ground Blackbutt (*Eucalyptus pilularis*) forest vegetation
729 assemblages. *Austral Ecology* 37, 767-778.
- 730 Lyons KG, Török P, Hermann J-M, Kiehl K, Kirmer A, Kollmann J, Overbeck GE, Tischew S, Allen
731 EB, Bakker JD, Brigham C, Buisson E, Crawford K, Dunwiddie P, Firn J, Grobert D, Hickman K,
732 Stradic SLE, Temperton VM (2023). Challenges and opportunities for grassland restoration: A
733 global perspective of best practices in the era of climate change. *Global Ecology and Conservation*
734 46, e02612.
- 735 Maccoll M, Tribe A, 2017. Wildlife Tourism and Conservation: The Hidden Vale Project In *Wildlife*
736 *Tourism, Environmental Learning and Ethical Encounters: Ecological and Conservation Aspects*
737 eds I. Borges de Lima, R.J. Green, pp. 33-41. Springer International Publishing, Cham.
- 738 Mahé I, Cordeau S, Bohan DA, Derrouch D, Dessaint F, Millot D, Chauvel B (2021). Soil seedbank:
739 old methods for new challenges in agroecology? *Annals of Applied Biology* 178, 23-38.
- 740 Mahood AL, Koontz MJ, Balch JK (2023). Fuel connectivity, burn severity, and seed bank
741 survivorship drive ecosystem transformation in a semiarid shrubland. *Ecology* 104, e3968.
- 742 Mandle L, Bufford J, Schmidt I, Daehler C (2011). Woody exotic plant invasions and fire: reciprocal
743 impacts and consequences for native ecosystems. *Biological Invasions* 13, 1815-1827.
- 744 Mazerolle MJ, 2023. AICcmodavg: Model selection and multimodel inference based on (Q)AIC(c).
745 R package version 2.3.3. <https://cran.r-project.org/package=AICcmodavg>
- 746 McCullagh P, 2019. Generalized linear models, 2nd edn. Routledge, New York.
- 747 McGillicuddy M, Popovic G, Bolker BM, Warton DI (2025). Parsimoniously fitting large multivariate
748 random effects in glmmTMB. *Journal of Statistical Software* 112, 1 - 19.
- 749 McIntyre S, Heard KM, Martin TG (2003). The relative importance of cattle grazing in subtropical
750 grasslands: does it reduce or enhance plant biodiversity? *Journal of Applied Ecology* 40, 445-457.
- 751 McIvor JG, Gardener CJ (1994). Germinable soil seed banks in native pastures in north-eastern
752 Australia. *Australian Journal of Experimental Agriculture* 34, 1113-1119.

- 753 Milberg P, Hansson ML (1994). Soil seed bank and species turnover in a limestone grassland.
754 *Journal of Vegetation Science* 5, 35-42.
- 755 Moreira B, Pausas JG (2012). Tanned or burned: the role of fire in shaping physical seed
756 dormancy. *PLoS ONE* 7, e51523.
- 757 Morgan JW (1998). Composition and seasonal flux of the soil seed bank of species-rich *Themeda*
758 *triandra* grasslands in relation to burning history. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 9, 145-156.
- 759 Morgan JW, Williams NS, 2015. The ecology and dynamics of temperate native grasslands in
760 south-eastern Australia In *Land of Sweeping Plains: managing and restoring the native grasslands*
761 *of South-Eastern Australia* eds N.S.G. Williams, A. Marshall, J.W. Morgan, pp. 61-85. CSIRO.
- 762 Morris EC (2000). Germination response of seven east Australian *Grevillea* species (*Proteaceae*)
763 to smoke, heat exposure and scarification. *Australian Journal of Botany* 48, 179-189.
- 764 Myers JA, Chase JM, Crandall RM, Jiménez I (2015). Disturbance alters beta-diversity but not the
765 relative importance of community assembly mechanisms. *Journal of Ecology* 103, 1291-1299.
- 766 Neldner V, Butler D, Guymer G, Fensham R, Holman J, Cogger H, Ford H, Johnson C, Holman J,
767 Butler D (2019). Queensland's Regional Ecosystems. Building and maintaining a biodiversity
768 inventory, planning framework and information system for Queensland. *Queensland Herbarium*
769 (*Queensland Department of Science, Information Technology and Innovation, Brisbane*).
- 770 Oksanen J, Simpson G, Blanchet F, Kindt R, Legendre P, Minchin P, O'Hara R, Solymos P,
771 Stevens M, Szoecs E, Wagner H, Barbour M, Bedward M, Bolker B, Borcard D, Carvalho G,
772 Chirico M, De Caceres M, Durand S, Evangelista H, FitzJohn R, Friendly M, Furneaux B, Hannigan
773 G, Hill M, Lahti L, McGlenn D, Ouellette M, Ribeiro Cunha E, Smith T, Stier A, Ter Braak C, Weedon
774 J, 2024. vegan: Community Ecology Package. R package version 2.6-8. [https://CRAN.R-](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan)
775 [project.org/package=vegan](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan)
- 776 Oliveras Menor I, Prat-Guitart N, Spadoni GL, Hsu A, Fernandes PM, Puig-Gironès R, Ascoli D,
777 Bilbao BA, Bacciu V, Brotons L, Carmenta R, de-Miguel S, Gonçalves LG, Humphrey G,
778 Ibarregaray V, Jones MW, Machado MS, Millán A, de Morais Falleiro R, Mouillot F, Pinto C, Pons
779 P, Regos A, Senra de Oliveira M, Harrison SP, Armenteras Pascual D (2025). Integrated fire
780 management as an adaptation and mitigation strategy to altered fire regimes. *Communications*
781 *Earth & Environment* 6, 202.
- 782 Ooi MKJ (2012). Seed bank persistence and climate change. *Seed Science Research* 22, S53-
783 S60.

- 784 Ooi MKJ, Denham AJ, Santana VM, Auld TD (2014). Temperature thresholds of physically dormant
785 seeds and plant functional response to fire: variation among species and relative impact of climate
786 change. *Ecology and Evolution* 4, 656-671.
- 787 Ooi MKJ, Tangney R, Auld TD, 2022. Fire and regeneration from seeds in a warming world, with
788 emphasis on Australia In *Plant Regeneration from Seeds* eds C.C. Baskin, J.M. Baskin, pp. 229-
789 242. Academic Press.
- 790 Orr D, Paton C, Blight G (1996). An improved method for measuring the germinable soil seed
791 banks of tropical pastures. *Tropical Grasslands* 30, 201-205.
- 792 Orr DM, Paton CJ, Playford C (2004). Dynamics of plant populations in *Heteropogon contortus*
793 (black speargrass) pastures on a granite landscape in southern Queensland. 2. Seed production
794 and soil seed banks of *H. contortus*. *Tropical Grasslands* 38, 31-41.
- 795 Orr DM, Yee MC, Rutherford MT, Paton CJ (2010). Impacts of grazing management options on
796 pasture and animal productivity in a *Heteropogon contortus* (black speargrass) pasture in central
797 Queensland. 2. Population dynamics of *Heteropogon contortus* and *Stylosanthes scabra* cv. *Seca*.
798 *Crop and Pasture Science* 61, 255-267.
- 799 Page MJ, Baxter GS, Lisle AT (2006). Evaluating the adequacy of sampling germinable soil seed
800 banks in semi-arid systems. *Journal of Arid Environments* 64, 323-341.
- 801 Palmer HD, Denham AJ, Ooi MKJ (2018). Fire severity drives variation in post-fire recruitment and
802 residual seed bank size of *Acacia* species. *Plant Ecology* 219, 527-537.
- 803 Pausas JG, Keeley JE (2023). Evolutionary fire ecology: An historical account and future
804 directions. *Bioscience* 73, 602-608.
- 805 Pausas JG, Lamont BB (2022). Fire-released seed dormancy - a global synthesis. *Biological*
806 *Reviews* 97, 1612-1639.
- 807 Peco B, Ortega M, Levassor C (1998). Similarity between seed bank and begetation in
808 Mediterranean grassland: a predictive model. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 9, 815-828.
- 809 Penman TD, Binns DL, Shiels RJ, Allen RM, Kavanagh RP (2008). Changes in understory plant
810 species richness following logging and prescribed burning in shrubby dry sclerophyll forests of
811 south-eastern Australia. *Austral Ecology* 33, 197-210.
- 812 Pérez-Invernón FJ, Gordillo-Vázquez FJ, Huntrieser H, Jöckel P (2023). Variation of lightning-
813 ignited wildfire patterns under climate change. *Nature Communications* 14, 739.

- 814 Pimm SL (1984). The complexity and stability of ecosystems. *Nature* 307, 321-326.
- 815 PlantNet, 2024. The NSW Plant Information Network System. Royal Botanic Gardens and Domain
816 Trust, Sydney. <https://plantnet.rbgsyd.nsw.gov.au/>, accessed February 2024
- 817 Plue J, Colas F, Auffret AG, Cousins SAO (2017). Methodological bias in the seed bank flora holds
818 significant implications for understanding seed bank community functions. *Plant Biology* 19, 201-
819 210.
- 820 Plue J, Hermy M (2012). Consistent seed bank spatial structure across semi-natural habitats
821 determines plot sampling. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 23, 505-516.
- 822 Plumanns Pouton E, Kasel S, Penman TD, Swan M, Kelly LT (2024). Soil seedbanks are shaped
823 by the timing of fires in a Mediterranean-type ecosystem. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 61, 2335-
824 2349.
- 825 Podani J, Schmera D (2011). A new conceptual and methodological framework for exploring and
826 explaining pattern in presence—absence data. *Oikos* 120, 1625-1638.
- 827 Prangel E, Kasari-Toussaint L, Neuenkamp L, Noreika N, Karise R, Marja R, Ingerpuu N, Kupper T,
828 Keerberg L, Oja E, Meriste M, Tiitsaar A, Ivask M, Helm A (2023). Afforestation and abandonment
829 of semi-natural grasslands lead to biodiversity loss and a decline in ecosystem services and
830 functions. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 60, 825-836.
- 831 Prober S, Lunt I (2009). Restoration of *Themeda australis* swards suppresses soil nitrate and
832 enhances ecological resistance to invasion by exotic annuals. *Biological Invasions* 11, 171-181.
- 833 Puig-Gironès R, Palmero-Iniesta M, Fernandes PM, Oliveras Menor I, Ascoli D, Kelly LT, Charles-
834 Dominique T, Regos A, Harrison S, Armenteras D, Brotons L, de-Miguel S, Spadoni GL, Carmenta
835 R, Machado M, Cardil A, Santos X, Erdozain M, Canaleta G, Berlinck CN, Vilalta-Clapés Q,
836 Mouillot F, Salis M, Verdinelli M, Bacciu V, Pons P (2025). The use of fire to preserve biodiversity
837 under novel fire regimes. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*
838 380, 20230449.
- 839 Pywell RF, Putwain PD, Webb NR (1997). The decline of heathland seed populations following the
840 conversion to agriculture. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 34, 949-960.
- 841 R Development Core Team, 2024. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R
842 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>

- 843 Rawson T, Davies R, Whalen M, Mackay D (2013). Fire-related cues and germination from the soil
844 seed bank of senescent remnants of mallee vegetation on Eastern Kangaroo Island. *Austral*
845 *Ecology* 38, 139-151.
- 846 Rose H, Rose C, 2020. Grasses of coastal NSW. NSW Agriculture.
- 847 Rose H, Rose C, Rose T, 2011. Legumes and herbs of coastal NSW. NSW Department of Industry
848 and Investment.
- 849 Rovithakis A, Grillakis MG, Seiradakis KD, Giannakopoulos C, Karali A, Field R, Lazaridis M,
850 Voulgarakis A (2022). Future climate change impact on wildfire danger over the Mediterranean: the
851 case of Greece. *Environmental Research Letters* 17, 045022.
- 852 Ryan KC, Knapp EE, Varner JM (2013). Prescribed fire in North American forests and woodlands:
853 history, current practice, and challenges. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 11, e15-e24.
- 854 Santana VM, Alday JG, Baeza MJ (2014). Effects of fire regime shift in Mediterranean Basin
855 ecosystems: changes in soil seed bank composition among functional types. *Plant Ecology* 215,
856 555-566.
- 857 Santana VM, Bradstock RA, Ooi MKJ, Denham AJ, Auld TD, Baeza MJ (2010). Effects of soil
858 temperature regimes after fire on seed dormancy and germination in six Australian Fabaceae
859 species. *Australian Journal of Botany* 58, 539-545.
- 860 Setterfield SA, Rossiter-Rachor NA, Hutley LB, Douglas MM, Williams RJ (2010). Turning up the
861 heat: the impacts of *Andropogon gayanus* (gamba grass) invasion on fire behaviour in northern
862 Australian savannas. *Diversity and Distributions* 16, 854-861.
- 863 Shi Y-F, Shi S-H, Jiang Y-S, Liu J (2022). A global synthesis of fire effects on soil seed banks.
864 *Global Ecology and Conservation* 36, e02132.
- 865 Simon BK, Alfonso Y, 2011. AusGrass2. <http://ausgrass2.myspecies.info/> Accessed 2024.
- 866 Stanley TD, Ross EM, 1983. Flora of south-eastern Queensland. State of Queensland Department
867 of Primary Industries.
- 868 Steffensen V, 2020. Fire Country: How Indigenous fire management could help save Australia.
869 CSIRO Publishing.
- 870 Stephens SL, Thompson S, Boisramé G, Collins BM, Ponisio LC, Rakhmatulina E, Steel ZL,
871 Stevens JT, van Wagtendonk JW, Wilkin K (2021). Fire, water, and biodiversity in the Sierra
872 Nevada: a possible triple win. *Environmental Research Communications* 3, 081004.

- 873 Sternberg M, Gutman M, Perevolotsky A, Kigel J (2003). Effects of grazing on soil seed bank
874 dynamics: an approach with functional groups. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 14, 375-386.
- 875 Stokes CA, MacDonald GE, Adams CR, Langeland KA, Miller DL (2011). Seed Biology and
876 Ecology of Natalgrass (*Melinis repens*). *Weed Science* 59, 527-532.
- 877 Tessema ZK, de Boer WF, Baars RMT, Prins HHT (2012). Influence of grazing on soil seed banks
878 determines the restoration potential of aboveground vegetation in a semi-arid savanna of Ethiopia.
879 *Biotropica* 44, 211-219.
- 880 Thompson K (1986). Small-scale heterogeneity in the seed bank of an acidic grassland. *Journal of*
881 *Ecology* 74, 733-738.
- 882 Tomat-Kelly G, Dillon WW, Flory SL (2021). Invasive grass fuel loads suppress native species by
883 increasing fire intensity and soil heating. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 58, 2220-2230.
- 884 Tubbesing CL, York RA, Stephens SL, Battles JJ (2020). Rethinking fire-adapted species in an
885 altered fire regime. *Ecosphere* 11, e03091.
- 886 Vandvik V, Klanderud K, Meineri E, Måren IE, Töpper J (2016). Seed banks are biodiversity
887 reservoirs: species–area relationships above versus below ground. *Oikos* 125, 218-228.
- 888 Vellend M, Lilley PL, Starzomski BM (2008). Using subsets of species in biodiversity surveys.
889 *Journal of Applied Ecology* 45, 161-169.
- 890 Ward D, Kirkman K, Morris C (2023). Long-term subtropical grassland plots take a long time to
891 change: Replacement is more important than richness differences for beta diversity. *Ecology and*
892 *Evolution* 13.
- 893 Watson P, Wardell-Johnson G (2008). Fire frequency and time-since-fire effects on the open-forest
894 and woodland flora of Girraween National Park, south-east Queensland, Australia. *Austral Ecology*
895 29, 225-236.
- 896 Watson PJ, Bradstock RA, Morris EC (2009). Fire frequency influences composition and structure
897 of the shrub layer in an Australian subcoastal temperate grassy woodland. *Austral Ecology* 34,
898 218-232.
- 899 Weeks J, Miller JED, Steel ZL, Batzer EE, Safford HD (2023). High-severity fire drives persistent
900 floristic homogenization in human-altered forests. *Ecosphere* 14.

901 Wester DB, Rideout-Hanzak S, Britton CM, Whitlaw H (2014). Plant community response to the
902 East Amarillo Complex wildfires in the Southern High Plains, USA. *Community Ecology* 15, 222-
903 234.

904 Wills TJ, Read J (2007). Soil seed bank dynamics in post-fire heathland succession in south-
905 eastern Australia. *Plant Ecology* 190, 1-12.

906 Wu H, Walker S, Rollin MJ, Tan DKY, Robinson G, Werth J (2007). Germination, persistence, and
907 emergence of flaxleaf fleabane (*Conyza bonariensis* [L.] Cronquist). *Weed biology and*
908 *Management* 7, 192-199.

909 Zhou Y, Singh J, Butnor JR, Coetsee C, Boucher PB, Case MF, Hockridge EG, Davies AB, Staver
910 AC (2022). Limited increases in savanna carbon stocks over decades of fire suppression. *Nature*
911 603, 445-449.

912

913 **Table 1:** Number of identified species (from a total of 117 species) from above-ground vegetation
 914 and below-ground seedbanks in grassy woodlands of southeast Queensland, Australia. The data
 915 were analysed as 13 functional trait groups, assigned hierarchically, such that a species could be
 916 included in both the Native Grass and the broader Grass group. Some species occurred in the
 917 above and below ground samples, meaning the total number of species \neq above + below.

Functional Group	Levels	Above	Below	Total no. species
Total	All species	78	73	117
Origin	Native	54	42	74
	Exotic	24	31	42
Life span	Annual	10	18	21
	Perennial	68	55	95
Growth form	Forb	37	46	64
	Grass	22	18	29
Origin x growth form	Native Grass	17	16	23
	Exotic Grass	5	2	6
	Native Forb	21	21	33
	Exotic Forb	13	25	28
Legume x growth form	Leguminous Forb	9	5	10
	Non-leguminous Forb	25	41	51

918
 919

920 **Table 2.** Coefficients from models examining the effects of position (above/below ground) and burn
 921 treatment (control/burn) on species richness (α diversity) for plant functional groups in grassy
 922 woodlands of southeast Queensland, Australia. In all models, the interaction term (position x burn)
 923 was not significant ($P < 0.05$) and was removed. The Intercept represents above-ground, unburnt
 924 control sites.

Functional group	Term	Estimate	Standard Error	z-value	P value
Total	Intercept	2.386	0.062	38.486	
	Position	0.905	0.064	14.145	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.099	0.058	1.709	0.087
Native	Intercept	2.019	0.076	26.534	
	Position	0.616	0.080	7.720	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.134	0.076	1.750	0.080
Exotic	Intercept	1.168	0.111	10.565	
	Position	1.396	0.112	12.439	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.052	0.090	0.582	0.561
Annual	Intercept	0.375	0.164	2.285	
	Position	1.514	0.167	9.093	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.016	0.128	0.128	0.898
Perennial	Intercept	2.230	0.068	33.024	
	Position	0.780	0.070	11.134	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.121	0.065	1.853	0.064
Forb	Intercept	1.544	0.092	16.826	
	Position	1.367	0.093	14.644	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.048	0.075	0.638	0.523
Grass	Intercept	1.161	0.117	9.916	
	Position	0.539	0.123	4.389	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.176	0.119	1.479	0.139
Native Grass	Intercept	0.812	0.137	5.917	
	Position	0.673	0.142	4.742	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.199	0.135	1.474	0.140
Exotic Grass	Intercept	-0.049	0.225	-0.216	
	Position	0.095	0.252	0.378	0.706
	Burn treatment	0.095	0.252	0.378	0.706
Native Forb	Intercept	1.075	0.120	8.997	
	Position	0.944	0.124	7.645	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.068	0.111	0.610	0.542
Exotic Forb	Intercept	0.364	0.160	2.281	
	Position	2.018	0.160	12.576	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.037	0.103	0.361	0.718
Leguminous forb	Intercept	0.175	0.205	0.851	
	Position	0.473	0.207	2.292	0.022
	Burn treatment	0.101	0.220	0.457	0.648
Non-leguminous forb	Intercept	1.152	0.110	10.493	
	Position	1.648	0.111	14.862	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.043	0.082	0.530	0.596

926 **Table 3.** Coefficients from models examining the effects of position (above/below ground) and burn
 927 treatment (control/burn) on the Local Contribution to β Diversity for plant functional groups in
 928 grassy woodlands of southeast Queensland, Australia. For all groups except exotic grass, an
 929 interaction term (position x burn) was insignificant ($P < 0.05$) and thus removed, leaving a final
 930 model with main effects of position and burn treatment. The Intercept represents above-ground,
 931 unburnt control sites.

Functional group	Term	Estimate	Standard Error	z-value	P value
Total	Intercept	-3.917	0.016	-238.056	
	Position	-0.366	0.019	-18.892	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.013	0.020	0.651	0.515
Native	Intercept	-3.952	0.023	-170.479	
	Position	-0.293	0.024	-12.018	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.022	0.029	0.740	0.459
Exotic	Intercept	-3.884	0.026	-150.377	
	Position	-0.433	0.032	-13.490	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.001	0.032	0.036	0.459
Annual	Intercept	-3.873	0.049	-78.905	
	Position	-0.330	0.042	-7.795	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.010	0.064	0.165	0.869
Perennial	Intercept	-3.921	0.016	-240.916	
	Position	-0.358	0.020	-17.847	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.015	0.020	0.752	0.452
Forb	Intercept	-3.901	0.018	-216.218	
	Position	-0.398	0.020	-19.706	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.007	0.023	0.311	0.756
Grass	Intercept	-3.941	0.040	-97.866	
	Position	-0.239	0.048	-4.935	<0.001
	Burn treatment	-0.048	0.048	-0.991	0.322
Native Grass	Intercept	-3.980	0.041	-97.733	
	Position	-0.173	0.048	-3.594	<0.001
	Burn treatment	-0.030	0.048	-0.634	0.526
Exotic Grass	Intercept	-3.220	0.237	-13.565	
	Position	-1.173	0.355	-3.302	0.001
	Burn treatment	-0.787	0.373	-2.110	0.035
	Position x burn	0.968	0.481	2.013	0.044
Native Forb	Intercept	-3.935	0.022	-180.698	
	Position	-0.321	0.027	-12.077	<0.001
	Burn treatment	0.011	0.026	0.437	0.662
Exotic Forb	Intercept	-3.791	0.038	-100.510	
	Position	-0.346	0.038	-9.211	<0.001
	Burn treatment	-0.004	0.047	-0.074	0.941
Leguminous Forb	Intercept	-3.666	0.046	-80.554	
	Position	-0.272	0.055	-4.964	<0.001
	Burn treatment	-0.044	0.055	-0.809	0.418
Non-leguminous Forb	Intercept	-3.887	0.026	-149.431	
	Position	-0.404	0.024	-16.996	<0.001

932	Burn treatment	0.022	0.034	0.663	0.507
-----	----------------	-------	-------	-------	-------

933 **Figure 1.** Location of ten transects, each consisting of three replicate quadrats, where the above
934 ground plant community and soil seedbanks were sampled in a subtropical grassy woodland. Each
935 transect in the 2022 burn area was paired with a nearby control transect, 50-200m away in similar
936 vegetation. The inset shows the location of the study area in southeast Queensland, Australia.

940 **Figure 2.** Of all identified species (n=117) from ten grassy woodland sites in southeast
941 Queensland, Australia, only 35 were common between the above- and below-ground plant
942 communities. In the above-ground vegetation 43 of 78 species (55%) did not occur below-ground
943 while 38 of the 73 species (52%) in the seedbank were unique to that position.

944
945

946 **Figure 3.** Effects of low-intensity prescribed fire (control vs burn) and position (above- vs below-
 947 ground) on (a) total species richness (α diversity) and (b) community uniqueness (Local
 948 Contribution (LC) to β diversity) in grassy woodlands of southeast Queensland, Australia. Plots
 949 show estimates from the final model (fire + position) and 95% confidence intervals. Raw data are
 950 shown as small points jittered along the x-axis to distinguish overlapping values. Total species
 951 richness (a) was affected position ($P < 0.001$) but not fire ($P = 0.087$), and a similar response
 952 observed in all other functional groups (Fig. S1). Total species LC β diversity (b) was affected
 953 position ($P < 0.001$) but not fire ($P = 0.515$) and a similar response was observed in all other
 954 groups except exotic grasses (Fig. S2).

955
 956
 957

958 **Figure 4.** Partitioning of pairwise dissimilarity (Jaccard) values among (a) above-, (d) below- and
 959 (c) above- and below-ground plant communities in grassy woodlands of southeast Queensland,
 960 Australia. Blue points are dissimilarities between quadrats within positions ((b) above vs above; (b)
 961 below vs below) and (c) black points are above- vs below-ground dissimilarities. The position on
 962 the triangle indicates the relative level of similarity, richness difference or replacement between two
 963 quadrats.

964

965

966 **Figure 5.** Principal Components Analysis (PCA) of above- and below-ground vegetation
 967 composition across burn and control sites, in grassy woodlands of southeast Queensland,
 968 Australia. a) The proportion of variance explained by each component. The first three principal
 969 components cumulatively explained 39.06% of variation in the data; b) Components 1 (28.66%
 970 variance explained) and 2 (6.28% of variance explained); c) Components 1 and 3 (4.12% of
 971 variance explained); and d) Components 2 and 3.

972
 973
 974
 975
 976